

International Conference: Intangible Cultural Heritage, Museums and Innovation (DAY 1)

The power of transformation

EVENT INFORMATION

PRACTICAL

PROGRAM

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Program

8h45	Coffee and registration
9h15	Welcome by Valérie Simonet (Cité Internationale de la tapisserie and Conseil Départemental de la Creuse) & Séverine Cachat (Maison des Cultures du Monde - Centre français du Patrimoine Culturel Immateriel)
9h35	Introduction: The Intangible Cultural Heritage & Museums Project
9h50	Intangible cultural heritage and museums: first results of the 2018 survey of the French Ministry of Culture - abstract by Isabelle Chave (French Ministry of Culture)
10h20	Coffee break
10h50	KEYNOTE - Museums, intangible cultural heritage and innovation through participatory methodologies - abstract by Filomena Sousa
11h35	The practitioner's voice. Interview with practitioners of intangible cultural heritage on collaborating with museums <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Aurelie Dumain (Musées départementaux Albert et Félicie Demard, dans le cadre de l'ethnopôle « Réinventons les musées populaires ») and Marie Boyard (Gang des chiffonniers)• Delphine Mangeret - 'cartonnière' (Cité internationale de la tapisserie et de l'art tissé)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paul Terral - Phare Ouest / Musée des arts et traditions populaires de Cancale
12h55	Lunch break
14h05	<p>Museums from throughout Europe present their inspiring cases on intangible cultural heritage and innovation (part 1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sylvie De Coster - Texture (BE): Biolace • Emmanuel Gérard - Cité internationale de la tapisserie (FR): Aubusson weaves Tolkien • Jantiene van Elk - TextielMuseum (NL): TextielLab • Frank Hemeltjen: Kenniscentrum Immaterieel Erfgoed Nederland / Nederlands Openluchtmuseum (NL): CraftsLab
15h25	Coffee break
15h55	<p>Museums from throughout Europe present their inspiring cases on intangible cultural heritage and innovation (part 2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sarah Kenderdine - Laboratory for Experimental Museology (CH): The Hong Kong Martial Arts Living Archive • Hilde Langerart - Industriemuseum (BE): Busy printing! The revival of printing techniques. The museum as a showcase and activity centre • Rosa Anna Di Lella - Museo delle Civiltà (IT): The Making of a Point of View. Spotlight on Indonesian and Malaysian collections • Ineke Steevens - NAVIGO (BE): The role of a participatory museum in safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage. The case of the shrimp fishers on horseback in Oostduinkerke (Flanders - Belgium) in a co-creative project
17h15	<p>Reflections on the day</p> <p>by Cécile Duvelle (former Chief of the Section of Intangible Heritage Section of UNESCO and Secretary of the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage)</p>
18h00	<p>Presentation of the collaboration between the Cité Internationale de la tapisserie & <u>Théâtre des Origines: 'PCI qu'es aquò?'</u></p>

Contact us

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